

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Lingering Challenges of Underdevelopment in Africa's and Nigeria: The Root Causes, Impacts and Panacea

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Abstract

The underdevelopment of Africa's and Nigeria is neither natural nor solely caused by internal contradictions, such as corruption, bad leadership, embezzlement of public funds as argued by some political science scholars even though the aforementioned internal factors plays a very devastating roles on the issue of underdevelopment in Africa. However, Andre G. Frank argued that the Europe and Africa's were developing at a different pace, until the Europe came and distorted the development of Africa, the idea which Frank called development of underdevelopment in Africa. Nevertheless, it is germane to expose the fact that the underdevelopment of Africa's and Nigeria was caused or could be traced to internal and external factors such as bad leadership, corruption and highhandedness etc. as the internal factors on one hand, and slavery, colonialism and imperialism, deceptive politics of exploitation of Africa's surplus values as the external factors on the other hand. However, this paper examined the external causes of underdevelopment in Africa's and Nigeria, and examined the pattern or process through which the Europe underdeveloped Africa's and Nigeria. This paper adopted the relative deprivation theory as a model to explaining how Africa's and Nigeria were deprived of her development, and how her resources were exploited by the Europe, hence, underdevelopment of Africa's and Nigeria. This paper also adopted the secondary methods of data gathering, as valuable data were retrieved from articles, textbooks, newspapers and internets materials, as those data collected are used to validate the arguments of this study. This paper finally proffers sustainable solutions on how to fall out of the devastating challenges of underdevelopment ravaging Africa's and Nigeria.

Keywords: underdevelopment, deprivation, exploitation, Africa's, Nigeria, Europe, colonialism, slavery.

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1. Introduction

It is very germane to note that association of men which is naturally characterized by exploitations and threat is inevitable, as threat and exploitation has always reflected in the actions of men in their relations with other men, either at individual relations level, group relations level and or countries relations level. Aristotle posits that no man is a highland; it has being in the character of men to associate with one another. He therefore submits that man is by nature a political animal (Aristotle, 384 BCE- 322 BCE). Associations of men and nations has always depict one forms of threat or the other as conflict, deprivation and exploitation has always reflected in the relations of men and nation with other men and nations respectively. It was on this bases that Hans Morgenthau argued that in the relations of state (countries) with one another, power is necessary to protect every state

national interests, and therefore argued that all states should seek power (Military, economic and diplomatic Capability) at all time in order to protect their interests (Morgenthau, 1948). As analyzed in Uhou Jerry in relations to Morgenthau submission, O.B.C Nwoli submits that politics whether national or international, ultimately and fundamentally the struggle for mind and resources of men and nation. He argued further that, in the struggle, the gladiators often used all methods to win, including deception, as those countries that are deceived lose freedom, power and resources and grow lean while those countries that deceived them gain those valuables and grow fat (See Uhou, 2014). States had naturally come in contact with one another, either on friendly relations, or hostile one through the activities of slavery and colonialism as experienced by many African states in the past. It was on this ground that the